

Methyl Red as an Adsorption Indicator (A Note).

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The mechanism of the adsorption of dyestuffs, specially of indicators by polar precipitates is of interest in relation to the use of 'adsorption indicators' in volumetric titrations. Quantitative estimations of the amount of indicators adsorbed by silver halides under different conditions of precipitations are being carried out in this laboratory with measurements of consequential changes in p_H values and specific conductivities. It is expected that these experiments would throw light on the mechanism of the adsorption of indicators by polar precipitates. The results (mean of two parallel experiments) given below indicate that

(a) the p_H is mostly on the acid side in agreement with previous observations of Basu in this laboratory that precipitation of silver halides by double decomposition from the pure neutral salts produces an acid reaction;

(b) that the manner of precipitation from the same amounts of the reactants affects the adsorption of the indicator and

(c) that the adsorption of the indicator probably affects to some extent the p_H of the final system.

Absorbent—AgCl (4×10^{-3} g. mol.). Adsorbate—Methyl red.

Time = 1 hr.

Condition of expt. (0.1N soln. used).	Indicator adsorbed $\times 10^4$.	With methyl red.		Without methyl red.	
		p_H .	Sp. conductivity. $\times 10^4$ at 35° .	p_H .	Sp. conductivity. $\times 10^4$ at 35° .
I. Equivalent amount.					
AgNO ₃ added to KCl.	0.31 g.	5.60	61.34	5.47	62.27
KCl ,, AgNO ₃	0.73	5.55	60.42	5.60	61.97

Condition of expt.	Indicator absorbed $\times 10^4$.	p_H .	Sp. conductivity. $\times 10^4$ at 35° .	p_H .	Sp. conductivity. $\times 10^4$ at 35° .
II. KCl in excess (5×10^{-5} g. mol.).			With methyl red.		Without methyl red.
AgNO ₃ added to KCl	0.58	5.72	59.84	6.40	63.45
KCl .. AgNO ₃	0.71	5.58	62.87	5.94	63.39
III. AgNO ₃ in excess (5×10^{-5} g.mol.).					
AgNO ₃ added to KCl	0.70	5.54	61.19	5.60	62.21
KCl .. AgNO ₃	2.1	5.52	61.66	5.82	62.42

The method used in determining the p_H and the adsorption of the indicator will be described when the results are published in full.

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